

NAMING OF TYPES OF EMBROIDERY

B.I. Boltayeva

Termiz State University teacher:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8304391>

Annotation: In the article, embroidery schools, their naming and application are written. The basis of the restoration of national values of teaching embroidery in higher educational institutions has been studied. Basic words and phrases: appliqué, joynamaz, zardevor, palak, kirpech, sozana, quilt, folk crafts.

Аннотация: В статье написаны школы вышивания, их названия и приложения. Изучено основание восстановления национальных ценностей обучения вышивке в высших учебных заведениях. Основные слова и словосочетания: аппликация, джойнамаз, зардевор, палак, кирпеч, созана, квилт, народные промыслы.

Embroidery is divided into the following specific types:

Appliqué is a Latin word for pasting, and it means decorating with tissue paper and other sewing. Application is a special type of embroidery, it has its own technology.

Joynamaz is a mat that is placed on the ground and prayed over. It is used by those who believe in Islam. It is imagined as a factor that separates a person from this world during prayer. Joynamaz is made of various fabrics, its three sides are sewn in the form of an altar, and it is used in mosques, madrasahs and homes.

Zardevor is a home appliance. It is an artistic piece decorated with silk, velvet, satin embroidery on the chest. Zardevor is hung on the ceiling or wall of the house, ceiling or wall of the newly married bride in Uzbeks and Tajiks. It is made of thread or silk, its width is 40-70 cm, and it is sewn to fit the wall of the intended house.

Palak is one of the largest and most expensive decorative items that hang on walls. The palak shows the sky and the full moon. In ancient times, it was made with white and gray embroidery. It differs from sozana by the size of its flowers and the embroidery on the ground.

Kirpech - kirpush, an artistic item used to decorate the house over clothes hung on a rack or hung on vertical spaces of the wall.

So`zana is also known as Suzana in Persian. It means sewn with a needle. A word is an art piece made by embroidery on fabric, and it is hung on the wall to decorate the room. It is made by embroidery on satin, velvet, silk and other fabrics.

Choyshab - Persian-Tajik ruyjo means night tent. The bed sheet is mainly placed on the mattress to hold it in place and cover it while lying down.

In higher education, our national values are in the correct organization of the student's activities, in the creative environment in the family, in raising young people to be true successors of the Uzbek folk art inherited from our ancestors, true to life. serves as an important factor in orientation. After all, today it is no secret that the 21st century in which we live is the century in which intellectual wealth reigns. Whoever does not realize this fact in

time, if the pursuit of intellectual wealth does not become the content of daily life for any nation and country, such a country will inevitably be left behind on the path of world development.

A student who has stepped into a higher education institution and begins to learn the secrets of embroidery observes and studies the shape of pattern elements, features of its compositional structure, the creations of the great craftsmen and masters of the East. Studying folk crafts helps students to develop artistic-aesthetic taste, creativity and acquire a number of useful skills and abilities, helps to identify and develop their creative abilities.

In the course of the experiment, we conducted interviews to find out the student's initial knowledge, skills and qualifications for creating pattern compositions, and from the answers we received from the questionnaire, it became clear that almost 75% of the students have a desire to master the art of embroidery in the future.

The means of using modern pedagogic and information and communication technologies in the teaching of "folk crafts" provide students with artistic training in folk crafts, and the practical training method of education ensures that they become more active. The ability of a student to work independently in the art of embroidery allows them to master the training in a high-quality manner.

It is important to introduce students to embroidery art schools.

During the Khanate era, the masters of folk art began to gather in cities such as Khiva, Ko`kan, Bukhara, and Samarkand. Most of the time, Ferghana and Bukhara painters came to Samarkand, and Kokhan Margilan masters came to Tashkent to decorate buildings. This plays a big role in the further development of embroidery schools, the creation of unique compositions, and the enrichment of the color complex. Although these embroideries are similar to each other, each school of embroidery is distinguished by its own rules, principles, work method, and color scheme.

Tashkent embroidery school. Tashkent embroideries are distinguished by their elegance and the gradual transition of colors to each other, strict adherence to a certain color scheme, and the frequent use of geometric and plant-like embroideries. Embroidery is often done in green hamma. Islamic embroideries are also widely used intricate girih embroideries with clearly stylized moon flower, cotton, ax, three leaves, shukufta, leaf flower and other elements.

Khiva embroidery school. Khiva embroidery is fundamentally different from Samarkand, Tashkent, Fergana, Bukhara. Blue and green colors are mostly used in Khiva embroidery. The composition of Islamic embroidery consists of a branch, margula, shukufta, leaf, pea, flower, simple moon. Many star-forming loops are used, and the middle is enriched with spiral Islamic embroidery. Khiva embroidery is generally made on the basis of mixed compositions.

Bukhara and Samarkand embroidery schools. Bukhara embroidery is distinguished by the complexity and attractiveness of its compositions. Bukhara embroideries are distinguished by the use of complex knots in a clear and precise size, and special attention is paid to the rhythm of leaves, fruits, and flowers in vegetable embroideries. Samarkand embroidery is similar to Tashkent and Fergana methods. Samarkand embroideries are distinguished by their very floweriness, their leaves and flowers are very dynamic and lively. The embroideries are first blue and then green. In order to further strengthen the above information in the minds of students, it is important to complete the following educational task.

Adabiyotlar:

- 1.Sodikova N. Madaniy yodgorliklar xazinasasi. -T.: «Fin». 1981 - 270 b.
- 2.Sodikova N. Uzbek milliy kiyimlari. XX-XIX asr- imp I 2001, - 304 b.
- 3.Uratsov M. B.Kashtado`zlik va to`qimachilik hunarlariga oid atamalar. O`zbek tili va adabiyoti. 1996. № 6-son. 47-49-6.
- 4.Gyul' E. Joynamozdagi ramzlar. //San'at. - 2001.3-son. — B.13-16.
- 5.Shomirzayev M. K. Combined In Technology Courses Use Of Technologies //The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 05. – C. 389-396.
- 6.Shomirzayev M. X., Karimov I. I. Innovative pedagogical technologies in teaching technology //T.:“Universitet. – 2020. – T. 125.

